

WELCOME

No Talking Allowed

Now that the experiment has begun, we ask that you do not talk. If you have a question while you are reading the instructions, please raise your hand and the experimenter will approach you and answer your question in private.

Turn Off Personal Electronics

Turn off and put away all mobile phones and other electronic equipment. Anyone seen using such items during the experiment will be excluded from participation in future experiments.

Complete Privacy

This experiment is structured so that no one, including the experimenters or the other participants, will ever know the personal decision or money earnings of anyone in the experiment. This is accomplished by a procedure in which you collect your earnings, contained in a sealed envelope, from a numbered mailbox that only you have the key for. Your privacy is guaranteed because neither your name nor your student ID number will appear on any form that records your decisions or your earnings in this experiment. The only identifying mark that will be used is the identification number on the mailbox key that has been given to you. You will collect your money payoffs with privacy by using a key, which opens a mailbox located in a room adjacent to this room. The key and mailbox are labeled with the same identification number. You are the only person who knows your identification number.

Three Rounds of Decisions

You will make a decision in each of three rounds in this experiment. **One round will be randomly selected for payoff at the end of the experiment.**

Random Matching and Anonymity

Before each round, you will be randomly matched with one other person in the lab to form a group of two. No one will learn the identity of the person in his or her group. You will be matched with a different person in each of the three rounds.

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Starting Balances

At the beginning of each round, each individual will be endowed with 10 tokens worth \$1 each, yielding an Individual Fund of \$10. Each two person group begins with a Group Fund of \$0.

Decision Task in Each Round

Each person will decide independently and privately whether or not to move any of his/her tokens from his/her own Individual Fund into the Group Fund. Each person can move an amount between the minimum specified amount for that round and the amount 10. Each token that a person adds to the Group Fund reduces the value of his/her Individual Fund by \$1. However, each token added to the Group Fund by a group member increases the value of the Group Fund by \$1.50.

Earnings in a Round

After both people in the group make their decisions, the Group Fund will be divided equally among the two individuals in the group. For each individual in the group, those earnings will be combined with the amount that the individual has remaining in his/her own Individual Fund.

Thus, a person's total earnings for each decision will equal the ending dollar value of tokens in his/her own Individual Fund plus one-half of the ending dollar value of tokens in the Group Fund.

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Three examples illustrate how the tokens moved to the Group Fund are related to the values of the Individual and Group Funds.

- If a person adds 0 tokens to the Group Fund, that reduces the value of his/her Individual Fund by \$0 and adds \$0 to the value of the Group Fund.
- If a person adds 6 tokens to the Group Fund, that reduces the value of his/her Individual Fund by \$6 and adds \$9 to the value of the Group Fund.
- If a person adds 10 tokens to the Group Fund, that reduces the value of his/her Individual Fund by \$10 and adds \$15 to the value of the Group Fund.

Practicing by Yourself

After you are sure that you understand these instructions, click on the Finished Reading Instructions box in the upper left corner of your monitor screen to signal that you are ready to begin the experiment. You will first be given the opportunity to practice entering decisions without money payoffs. You will be able to enter trial decisions for yourself and the other person in your group and observe the resulting hypothetical payoffs for both people.

Making the Real Decisions

After everyone finishes their practice decisions, you all will be able to make your decisions in each of the three rounds.

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